

Heterocyclic Systems containing Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom. Facile Synthesis of Spiro-[anthrane-3, 9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine], Novel and Hitherto Unknown Heterocyclic System

JAG MOHAN*, G. S. R. ANJANEYULU and DINESH MADAN
Department of Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak-124 001

Manuscript received 31 May 1990, revised 12 December 1990,
accepted 25 April 1991

IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of biologically active bridgehead nitrogen heterocyclic system, we report here the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of novel hitherto unknown heterocyclic system, spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine] starting from anthrone (1).

Spiro[anthrane-3,9'-1,2,4,5-tetrahydro-s-tetrazine]-6-thione (2), obtained by the reaction of anthrone (1) with thiocarbonylhydrazide following the reported method, on condensation with α -halogenoketones and 1,2-dibromoethane furnished 6-aryl-spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine] hydrogen halides (5) and 6,7-dihydro-spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine]hydrobromide (6) respectively (Scheme 1). The structures 5

were obtained directly by heating 2 with ethyl chloroacetate and aldehydes in presence of pyridine and piperidine. The structures 3 and 4 were supported by their ir spectra. The parent thiazolidinone (3) absorbed at 1 720 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) but the exocyclic double bond at 7-position being in conjugation with carbonyl group at 6-position produced a bathochromic shift³ in the carbonyl absorption (1 695 cm^{-1}) of 4. The structure 3 was further established by its pmr spectral data.

Compounds 3, 4 ($\text{Ar}=\text{p-OCH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$), 5 ($\text{R}=\text{p-Cl-C}_6\text{H}_4$ -) and 6 were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive bacterium, *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungus *Candida albicans* by neat samples and serial plate dilution method⁴. The minimum inhibitory concentration of compound 4 ($\text{Ar}=\text{p-OCH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$ -) against *C. albicans* was found to be 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, and 3 was found to be active when tested as neat sample.

Experimental

Tlc was run on silica-gel plates using acetone-benzene (1 : 3) as irrigant. M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Spiro[anthrane-3,9'-1,2,4,5-tetrahydro-s-tetrazine]-6-thione (2): It was prepared by the reaction of a solution of anthrone (1) in ethanol with thiocarbonylhydrazide solution in 1N acetic acid, according to the reported method² (53%), m.p. 205° (Found: N, 20.19; S, 11.74. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires; N, 19.86; S, 11.35%; ν_{max} 1 100(C=S), 3 150 and 3 400 cm^{-1} (NH).

Spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine]-6(7H)-one (3): A mixture of 2 (0.94 g, 0.0033 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.32 g, 0.0033 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.55 g, 0.0066 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (150 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight at room temperature and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as orange-red needles (0.6 g, 56%), m.p. 225° (Found: C, 63.68; H, 4.61; N, 16.97; S, 10.23. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ requires: C, 63.35; H, 4.35; N, 17.39; S, 9.94%; ν_{max} 1 570 (C-N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 720 ($\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 3 210 and 3 280 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (CDCl_3) 4.60 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.85 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 7.05 (2H, s, 2xNH) and 7.30-8.30 (8H, m, ArH).

6-(p-Chlorophenyl)-spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine] hydrobromide (5a; R=p-Cl-C₆H₄-): A mixture of 2 (1.41 g, 0.005 mol) and p-chlorophenacyl bromide (1.17 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (150 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h and then the mixture was concentrated. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as brown shining flakes, (0.6 g, 54%), m.p. 242°d (Found: C, 55.69; H, 3.41; N, 11.54; S, 6.28. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{SBrCl}$ requires: C,

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{H}_2\text{NHNCSNH}_2$, (ii) $\text{Cl-CH}_2\text{COOH}$, NaOAc , (iii) ArCHO , NaOAc , (iv) $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COOEt}$, pyridine, ArCHO , piperidine, (v) RCOCH_2X , (vi) $\text{BrCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$.

and 6 were supported by ir and pmr spectral data. Lack of absorption at 1 660-1 700 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of 5 showed the absence of a carbonyl group suggesting thereby a cyclic structure. Similarly, 2 on condensation with chloroacetic acid, resulted in the formation of spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine]-6(7H)-one (3). 7-Arylidene-spiro[anthrane-3,9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine]-6(7H)-ones (4) were prepared by the following two routes. In the first route, 3 was condensed with aldehydes, while in the other, these

55.48; H, 3.62; N, 11.26; S, 6.43%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 620 (C=C, C=N) and 3 240 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (CDCl_3) 2.58 (2H, s, 2×NH), 3.97 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.75 (1H, s, NH), 6.93 (1H, s, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$), 6.70–7.52 (8H, m, ArH of anthrane system), 7.86 (4H, ABq, J 6 Hz (*ortho*-coupling), *p*-chlorophenyl protons).

Similarly, **5b–d** were prepared. All the compounds gave correct analytical results for C, H, N and S. Their m.p.s and yields are as follows: **5b** (R = C_6H_5), (34%), m.p. 236°; **5c** (R = *p*-Br- C_6H_4), (23%), m.p. 238°; **5d** (R = *p*-NO₂- C_6H_4), (53%), m.p. 230°d.

6, 7-Dihydrospiro[anthrane-3, 9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine]hydrobromide (6): A mixture of **2** (0.94 g, 0.0033 mol) and dibromoethane (0.63 g, 0.0033 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and then allowed to cool to the room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from DMF-ethanol as brown shining flakes (0.4 g, 31%), m.p. 234° (Found: C, 52.74; H, 4.21; N, 14.85; S, 7.86. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: C, 52.44; H, 4.37; N, 14.40; S, 8.23%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 520 (C–N), 1 610 (C=N) and 3 100 cm^{-1} (NH).

7-(p-Methoxybenzylidene)-spiro[anthrane-3, 9'-(4H)-[2H]-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine]-one (4); Ar = *p*-OCH₃- C_6H_4 . **Method (a)**: A mixture of **3** (0.85 g, 0.0025 mol), *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.34 g, 0.0025 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.41 g, 0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as light brown shining flakes (0.6 g, 54%), m.p. 245° (Found: C, 67.76; H, 4.28; N, 12.35; S, 7.68. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires: C, 68.18; H, 4.54; N, 12.73; S, 7.27%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 540 (C–N), 1 610, 1 630 (C=C, C=N), 1 690 (C=O) and 3 160 cm^{-1} (NH).

Method (b): A mixture of **2** (1.41 g, 0.005 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.61 g, 0.005 mol), pyridine (0.45 ml) and anhydrous ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 4 h. *p*-Methoxybenzaldehyde (0.68 g, 0.005 mol) and piperidine (0.35 ml) were then added to it and the mixture was refluxed further for 4 h, cooled and poured into water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as brown shining flakes (0.9 g, 41%), m.p. and m.m.p. 244°.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. D. R. Arora, Department of Microbiology, Medical College, Rohtak, for biological screening, to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (G.S.R.A.) and to Head of the Chemistry Department, Maharshi Dayanand University, for facilities.

References

1. JAG MOHAN, G. S. R. ANJANEYULU and KIRAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 570, 731 and references cited therein.
2. R. W. LAMON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 756.
3. H. M. RANDALL, R. G. FOWLER, N. FUSON and J. R. DANGLE, "Infrared determination of Organic Structures", Van Nostrand, New York, 1949.
4. H. NAKAHARA, T. ISHIKAWA, Y. SARAI, T. KONDO and S. MITSUHASHI, *Nature*, 1977, **266**, 165.